

Search for New Insecticides: Part I

A. K. Sen Gupta and J. Kumar

oo-Diethyl and dibutyl chlorothiophosphates have been condensed with several substituted phenols containing alkyl, halogen and unsaturated groupings to yield compounds of the type of the well-known insecticide, Parathion.

In aromatic derivatives of phosphoric acid and thiophosphoric acid, the nature of the substituents in the benzene ring has been found to play an important role in determining the insecticidal activity.¹ Activity appears when one of the substituent groups is acidic in nature² and high activity is also associated with a chemical function of acid anhydride character when one of the acids is a substituted phosphoric acid.³

With a view to studying the effect of various substituents on the insecticidal activity, several phenols were therefore condensed with *oo*-dialkyl chlorothiophosphate, prepared according to Fletcher *et al.*⁴ Thiophosphoryl chloride was prepared after the method of Belar Jr.⁵

EXPERIMENTAL

oo-Dibutyl Chlorothiophosphate.—Thiophosphoryl chloride (20 g.) in benzene (50 ml.) was added under constant stirring to a solution of sodium-*n*-butoxide (from 5.5 g. of Na in 75 ml. of *n*-butanol), the reaction temperature being kept at 5°-10°. The product distilled at 152°/5mm, yield 59%. (Found: C, 37.98; H, 6.8. Calc: C, 38.95; H, 7.30%. Found: S, 12.6, Calc 13.60%.

oo-Dialkyl *O*-Substituted Phosphorothionate.—A mixture of corresponding *oo*-dialkyl chlorothiophosphate (1*M*), anhydrous sodium salt of the substituted phenol (1*M*), and ethanol was refluxed for 1 hr., cooled to 20°, filtered, and the filtrate concentrated in vacuum. The residue was heated for a short period to remove the unchanged *oo*-dialkyl chlorothiophosphate. The crude product was dissolved in toluene, washed with 5% sodium carbonate and then with water. After drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate, toluene was removed under reduced pressure and the product distilled. The b.p., yields and analytical data are recorded in Tables I and II.

1. Metcalf, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1949, 42, 721.
2. Metcalf *et al*, *ibid.*, 1950, 43, 620.
3. Schrader, B.I.O.S. Final Report, pp. 714, 1005, 1608.
4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3943.
5. "Inorganic Synthesis," Vol. IV, p. 71.

TABLE I

oo-Diethyl *o*-substituted phosphorothionate

R	B.P.	Yield	Formula	Found	Reqd.
1. 4- <i>t</i> -butyl	141°/19mm	60%	C ₁₄ H ₂₃ O ₃ PS	C: 55.2% H: 7.1 S: 10.4	55.62% 7.61 10.59
2. 2-Methoxy-4-allyl	125°/27	60	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₄ PS	C: 52.00 H: 6.54 S: 9.88	53.16 6.64 10.10
3. 2-Methoxy-4- <i>iso</i> -allyl	115°/20	60	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₄ PS	C: 52.1 H: 6.51 S: 10.20	53.16 6.64 10.10
4. 4- <i>sec</i> -Amyl	90°/15	60	C ₁₃ H ₂₃ O ₃ PS	C: 55.9 H: 7.20 S: 10.00	56.96 7.06 10.10
5. <i>p</i> -Chloro	90°/6	50	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₃ PSCl	C: 41.76 H: 4.60 S: 11.20	42.78 4.99 11.40
6. <i>o</i> -Chloro	95°/10	50	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₃ PSCl	C: 42.2 H: 4.50 S: 11.25	42.78 4.99 11.40
7. 2-Chloro-4- <i>t</i> -butyl	115°/10	65	C ₁₄ H ₂₃ O ₃ PSCl	C: 48.94 H: 6.10 S: 9.30	49.94 6.53 9.50

TABLE II

R	B.P.	Yield	Formula	% of Carbon	
				Found	Reqd.
1. <i>p</i> - <i>tert</i> -butyl	155°/20mm	60%	C ₁₉ H ₃₃ O ₃ PS	C: 60.1% H: 8.70 S: 8.60	61.3% 8.87 8.60
2. <i>o</i> -Chloro	110°/8	50	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O ₃ PSCl	C: 48.9 H: 5.92 S: 9.40	49.94 6.69 9.50
3. <i>p</i> -Chloro	135°/8	60	C ₁₄ H ₂₃ O ₃ PSCl	C: 49.80 H: 6.43 S: 9.45	49.94 6.53 9.50

TABLE II (Contd.)

R	B.P.	Yield	Formula	% of Carbon	
				Found.	Reqd.
4. 3-Chloro-4-4-butyl	145°/8	60%	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₃ PSCl	C: 54.90%	53.04%
				H: 7.80	7.64
				S: 8.00	8.10
5. 2,6-Dibromo-4-nitro	82°/3	58	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₃ PSBr ₂ N	C: 32.40	33.27
				H: 3.85	3.85
				S: 6.20	6.30
6. 2-Methoxy-4-allyl	100°/3	58	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O ₄ PS	C: 57.50	58.08
				H: 7.76	7.79
				S: 8.63	8.60
7. 2-Methoxy-4-iso-allyl.	170°/4	60	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O ₄ PS	C: 57.90	58.08
				H: 7.12	7.79
				S: 8.45	8.60

The insecticidal activity of these compounds is under investigation and will be communicated in due course.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received November 19, 1965.